

Synthesis and antimicrobial screening of novel bis-triazolo-dithiadiazines containing bridgehead nitrogen

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Abstract : 1,4-Bis-(3-arylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzenes have been synthesized by treating 1,4-bis-(4-amino-3-mercapto-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazol-5-yl)-benzene with *N*-aryl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chlorides and then basification with dilute ammonia solution. Synthesis of 1,4-bis-(4-amino-3-mercapto-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazol-5-yl)-benzene was carried out by interacting the terephthalic acid dihydrazide with carbondisulphide in presence of potassium hydroxide and then by adding the hydrazine hydrate. Bis-triazolo-dithiadiazines on acetylation afforded di-acetyl derivatives. Structures of title compounds were delineated on the basis of determination of equivalent weight, chemical transformation, elemental analysis and spectral studies. These compounds have been assayed for their antibacterial and antifungal activity against various micro-organisms.

Keywords : Novel bis-triazolo-dithiadiazines, synthesis, antimicrobial activity.

Introduction

Sulphur and nitrogen containing heterocyclic compounds possess a wide range of biological activities^{1,2}. Synthesis of substituted [1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines have been reported earlier and found to be the active against various micro-organisms³⁻⁵. Compounds containing [1,2,4]-triazole and [1,2,4]-triazole-3-one were found to be therapeutically effective for number of pathological conditions including inflammation, tuberculosis, cancer, pain, hypertension etc.^{6,7}. Fused [1,2,4]-triazoles are found to possess various medicinal properties with diverse applications^{8,9}. The reagent *N*-aryl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride has enough potentiality in the synthesis of nitrogen and sulphur containing heterocyclic compounds. Its synthetic applications have been investigated earlier^{10,11}. On perusal of literature, it has been observed that there is scanty work on the synthesis of bis-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines. In view of these findings and as a part of wider programme to provide alternative routes of synthesis^{12,13}, synthesis of bis-(substituted)-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazines is reported.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded using the Veego, VMP-

D digital melting point apparatus and are uncorrected. Chemicals used were of A.R. grade. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker Avance II 400 NMR spectrometer using the solvents CDCl₃ and DMSO-*d*₆ with TMS as internal standard. IR spectra were recorded in Nujol mull and as KBr pellete on Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer in the range 4000–400 cm⁻¹. Purity of the compounds was checked by thin layer chromatography on silica gel-G plates.

The reagents *N*-aryl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chlorides were prepared by passing the chlorine gas (0.01 mol) through the solution of aryl isothiocyanates (0.01 mol) in chloroform (10 ml), maintaining the temperature at 10 °C. The reaction mixture was then diluted with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) and the solvent was distilled off under vacuum to get pale yellow coloured oily liquids (**3a-g**); ν_{\max} 1652, 1703 (C=N), 840 cm⁻¹ (C-S).

The parent compound terephthalic acid dihydrazide (**1**) was synthesized by refluxing terephthalic acid (0.01 mol) with thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) for 30 min, followed by the slow addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) with constant stirring.

Synthesis of 1,4-bis-(4-amino-3-mercapto-4H-[1,2,4]-

triazol-5-yl-benzene (2) :

The compound 1,4-bis-(4-amino-3-mercapto-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazol-5-yl-benzene (**2**) was synthesized by interacting the terephthalic acid dihydrazide (**1**) (0.01 mol) with carbondisulphide (0.02 mol) in presence of potassium hydroxide solution (2 *M*, 10 ml) and then by adding the hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol) slowly with constant stirring. The reaction mixture then stirred for 30 min at room temperature, cooled and poured in distilled water to obtain a white precipitate. It was crystallized from ethanol, (**2**) (80%), m.p. 214 °C(d).

*Synthesis of 1,4-bis-(3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzene (4a)* :

The compound 1,4-bis-(4-amino-3-mercapto-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazol-5-yl-benzene (**2**) (0.01 mol) was refluxed with *N*-phenyl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chloride (**3a**) (0.02 mol) over a water bath for 2 h using chloroform as solvent. Hydrogen chloride gas was evolved continuously. The reaction mixture was cooled and solvent was distilled off to afford a sticky mass, which on washing with petroleum ether (60–80 °C) gave a granular solid. On testing, it was found to be acidic to litmus. It on basification with dilute ammonia solution afforded a free base, 1,4-bis-(3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzene (**4a**). It was crystallized from ethanol, (70%), m.p. 140 °C (Found : C, 49.72; H, 2.66; N, 23.77; S, 22.02. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₆N₁₀S₄ : C, 50.34; H, 2.79; N, 24.47; S, 22.37%; ν_{\max} : 3423 (NH), 1609, 1588, 1502 (C=N), 1315, 1296 (C-N), 1230 (N-N), 743, 693 (C-S), 499 cm⁻¹ (S-S); δ (CDCl₃+DMSO-*d*₆) : 9.65 (2H, s, NH), 6.89–7.54 (14H, m, Ar-H); MS : *m/z* 495 (M⁺-C₆H₅), 481 (M⁺-N-C₆H₅), 324 (M⁺-C₃HN₄S₂-N-C₆H₅), 248 (C₃HN₄S₂-N-C₆H₅⁺), 171 (C₃HN₄S₂-N⁺), 157 (C₃HN₄S₂⁺)^{19,20}. The above reaction was extended to synthesize compounds (**4b-g**) : **4b** (72%), m.p. 172 °C (Found : C, 51.07; H, 3.39; N, 22.96; S, 20.88. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₀N₁₀S₄ : C, 52.00; H, 3.33; N, 23.33; S, 21.33%; ν_{\max} : 3418 (NH), 1618, 1596 (C=N), 1320, 1306 (C-N), 1224 (N-N), 740, 698 (C-S), 498 cm⁻¹ (S-S); δ (CDCl₃+DMSO-*d*₆) : 9.60 (2H, s, NH), 6.89–7.54 (12H, m, Ar-H), 2.38 (6H, s, Ar-CH₃); **c** (80%), m.p. 204 °C (Found : C, 50.81; H, 3.21; N, 23.37; S, 21.08.

Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₀N₁₀S₄ : C, 52.00; H, 3.33; N, 23.33; S, 21.33%; **d** (60%), m.p. 220 °C (Found : C, 52.10; H, 3.22; N, 22.94; S, 21.11. Calcd. for C₂₆H₂₀N₁₀S₄ : C, 52.00; H, 3.33; N, 23.33; S, 21.33%; **e** (70%), m.p. 222 °C (Found : C, 44.12; H, 2.21; N, 21.52; S, 19.05. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₄N₁₀S₄Cl₂ : C, 44.92; H, 2.18; N, 21.84; S, 19.96%; **f** (65%), m.p. 200 °C (Found : C, 43.91; H, 2.07; N, 21.66; S, 19.81. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₄N₁₀S₄Cl₂ : C, 44.92; H, 2.18; N, 21.84; S, 19.96%; **g** (75%), m.p. 183 °C (Found : C, 44.38; H, 2.11; N, 21.79; S, 19.41. Calcd. for C₂₄H₁₄N₁₀S₄Cl₂ : C, 44.92; H, 2.18; N, 21.84; S, 19.96%).

*Synthesis of 1,4-bis-(4-acetyl-3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzene (5a)* :

The 1,4-bis-(3-phenylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzene (**4a**) (0.01 mol) was refluxed with acetic anhydride (0.02 mol) and glacial acetic acid (10 ml) 2.5 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and poured in a ice cold water, a cream coloured solid precipitated was crystallized from aqueous ethanol to give (**5a**), (73%), m.p. 224 °C (Found : C, 50.52; H, 2.94; N, 21.30; S, 19.45. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₀N₁₀O₂S₄ : C, 51.21; H, 3.04; N, 21.34; S, 19.51%; ν_{\max} : 1698 (C=O), 1612, 1591 (C=N), 1345, 1321 (C-N), 1243 (N-N), 709, 695 (C-S), 489 cm⁻¹ (S-S); δ (CDCl₃+DMSO-*d*₆) : 6.68–7.35 (14H, m, Ar-H), 2.11 (6H, s, CH₃). The above reaction was extended to synthesize compounds (**5b-g**) : **5b** (72%), m.p. 155 °C; **c** (78%), m.p. 209 °C; **d** (68%), m.p. 166 °C; **e** (70%), m.p. 202 °C; **f** (75%), m.p. 233 °C; **g** (72%), m.p. 199 °C.

Results and discussion

Terephthalic acid dihydrazide (**1**) has been synthesized by refluxing the terephthalic acid (0.01 mol) with thionyl chloride (0.02 mol) for 30 min, followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol). It was transformed into 1,4-bis-(4-amino-3-mercapto-4*H*-[1,2,4]-triazol-5-yl-benzene (**2**) by treating with carbondisulphide (0.02 mol) and potassium hydroxide (2 *M*, 10 ml) followed by the addition of hydrazine hydrate (0.02 mol). Compound (**2**) was then refluxed with *N*-aryl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbamoyl chlorides (**3a-g**) (0.02 mol) for 2 h in chloroform medium. Hydrogen chloride gas was evolved which was

tested with litmus paper. The reaction mixture was cooled and chloroform was distilled off to afford sticky masses, which then washed with petroleum ether to get granular solids. All these compounds were acidic to litmus and on titrimetric analysis found to be the hydrochlorides. These were acidified with dilute ammonia solution to afford free bases, 1,4-bis-(3-arylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-*c*]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzenes (**4a-g**). The reagents *N*-aryl-*S*-chloro isothiocarbonyl chlorides were prepared by passing the chlorine gas (0.01 mol) through the solution of aryl isothiocyanates (0.01 mol) in chloroform (10 ml), maintaining the temperature at 10 °C, followed by the distillation of solvent under vacuum^{10,11}. Compounds (**4a-g**) on acetylation with acetic anhydride in 1 : 2 ratio afforded di-acetyl derivatives (**5a-g**) (Scheme 1).

Antimicrobial activity :

The antibacterial screening of synthesized compounds (**4a-g**) was carried out by cup plate diffusion method^{14,15} and both Gram-positive as well as Gram-negative strains like *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *S. typhi*, *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes* were used. Sensitivity plates were seeded with a bacterial inoculum of 1×10^6 CIU ml⁻¹ and each well (diameter 10 mm) was loaded with 0.1 ml of test compound solution (1000 µg ml⁻¹) in DMF, so that concentration of each test compound was 100 µg ml⁻¹. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 24 h at 37 °C, using vernier caliper. Inhibition zone record of the compounds indicated that (**4b**), (**4c**) and (**4d**) were highly active against *E. coli* and moderately active against *S. typhi* and *S. aureus*. Majority of the compounds were

Scheme 1

found inactive against *B. subtilis* and *A. aerogenes* (Table 1).

The minimum inhibitory concentration (MIC) was determined by serial dilution technique¹⁶ using nutrient broth medium. Against *E. coli*, the MIC values of com-

Table 1. Antimicrobial activity of compounds (**4a-h**)

Compd.	Antibacterial activity					Antifungal activity	
	<i>E. coli</i>	<i>S. aureus</i>	<i>S. typhi</i>	<i>B. subtilis</i>	<i>A. aerogenes</i>	<i>A. niger</i>	
						(Conc. 1%)	(Conc. 2%)
4a	+	+	+	-	-	-	-
4b	+++	++	++	+	+	+++	+++
4c	+++	++	++	+	-	+	+
4d	+++	++	++	-	+	+++	+++
4e	+	+	++	+	+	+	++
4f	+	+	+	-	-	-	+
4g	+	+	-	+	-	++	++

(-) : 12 mm and less (inactive), (+) : 13-16 mm (weakly active),

(++) : 17-20 mm (moderately active), (+++) : 21 mm and above (highly active).

pounds (4b), (4c) and (4d) were found to be 82, 79 and 75 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$ respectively.

On screening of the compounds (4b-g) for antifungal activity using paper disc method^{17,18}; (4b) and (4d) were found to be highly active against *A. niger*, whereas other compounds have low to moderate activity. The zones of inhibition were recorded after incubation for 48 h at 37 °C (Table 1).

Conclusion

The present work deals with the synthesis of 1,4-bis-(3-arylimino-[1,2,4]-triazolo-[3,4-c]-[1,2,4,5]-dithiadiazin-6-yl)-benzenes (4a-g) and their di-acetyl derivatives (5a-g). The method of synthesis is simple, much more efficient and requires short period of time. Antimicrobial study of title compounds showed that, compounds (4b), (4c) and (4d) have very good antimicrobial activities.

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